

Open, FAIR and robust research data

Interview with Anne ter Wal, David Colling, Ian McArdle, Wayne Peters

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Wayne Peters is the Research Data Manager, based in Library Services at Imperial College London, and a member of the FAIR Data Working Group.

Khan, Hamid 3:19

Can you give some background about current practices and procedures around data transparency and quality, either at Imperial in general or specifically in your department?

McArdle, Ian J 3:48

Within the department, what we are after is, rather than generating that ourselves, trying to find those records of transparency and quality so that we can try to ensure there is compliance. We don't have as much to do in that area ourselves in terms of generation of data or supporting people, except [that] we're involved in the implementation of systems to support that.

Currently we're involved in the FAIR [FAIR data principles: findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability] Data Repository project to try to increase the completeness of that information within the College.

Colling, David J 5:32

My day job is Professor of Physics and e-Science. I do a lot of work on the datasets for the LHC [Large Hadron Collider].

As part of being Director of Research Data Strategy, I was wanting to form the FAIR Data group. It's taken us a while, and it's been a lot [tougher] to pass than we thought, but we think we've come up on the right path. And we are looking at how to make data truly FAIRly available. We've chosen AI [Artificial Intelligence] technology for the repository, and that's been worked on with the help of outside contractor called Cottage Labs. But that's only one part of making data truly FAIRly available. It involves many other aspects.

Khan, Hamid 7:31

Anne, specifically with that business/social sciences side, what is some of the work that's going on there that you're aware of?

ter Wal, Anne 8:13

It'd be useful to separate data transparency from open data availability. In the social sciences, including business, there's been quite a lot of progress in being more transparent about how data will be used. In research that involves social science experiments, one important step has been most journals these days would expect this research to be not only pre-registered – there's an Open Science forum where this type of research is pre-registered – but also to make all the study materials available for peer review.

Research that follows the experimental paradigm has probably gone the furthest in making research methods transparent. This is less the case in research surveillance on archival data – for example, survey-based research or qualitative interview-based research. But also, journals are increasingly ramping up the expectations when it comes to the transparency of research methods and research data.

Where progress has been very slow is in making the actual data that comes out of research available publicly. In research that is more experimental in nature, that's probably where they've gone the furthest. And I think the reason why, in the social sciences, this is complicated is [that] often research data might be covered by

confidentiality agreements. For example, if you work with large corporates, have an opportunity to interview their staff, most organisations will understandably be quite reluctant to have this sit anywhere else than with the research team. Also, I think there is probably quite a bit of resistance because collecting these types of datasets is time-intensive and expensive, so most people wouldn't necessarily want to make this available for other people to use quite so early on.

In terms of the transparency of how data are collected, analysed, used, [and] stored, there's been a lot of progress, and most journals would have very high expectations and standards to uphold. When it comes to making data available for further research, there's quite limited progress.

Peters, Wayne 10:57

The short answer is that most of the areas that we cover under the umbrella term "research data management" [RDM] are in some way concerned with transparency and quality. But there's a longer answer to data quality.

We are concerned with transparency across the whole lifecycle, but a lot of our attention is focussed on transparency when it comes to sharing data, which follows from the point that Anne was making, which is why we talk about the FAIR principles. Particularly if there are issues about confidentiality, commercial sensitivity and so on, then the more transparency [there is about] how the data were obtained, how the data are being shared, and the various consents [and] permissions, [the easier it is] to share in a way that doesn't compromise legal or ethical issues.

On data quality, I'll give the long answer in case we end up talking about different things, because data quality is also a specific topic within research data management. There's the broader sense, where many of the topics we cover are about data quality, including things like documentation, metadata and so on. But it is [a] specific topic within the RDM curriculum, which is primarily focussed [on] standards and workflows for preventing or minimising error, or checking for and rectifying errors. It's a narrower focus, but I think it's also important.

It's not necessarily a core topic in all RDM curricula. We don't have a separate webpage on it at the moment, which we probably should do, but I do mention it in

training and workshops, often in passing. Part of the reason for that is because, similar to metadata, it's often quite a difficult topic to provide support and guidance on as a generalist. A lot of it does depend on what researchers are doing in their research. When I talk about it in training, I often use domain-agnostic examples, so I talk about spreadsheet good practice, data validation rules and processes for managing data input and then data-checking. Spreadsheets [are] a good domain-agnostic way of talking about that. That may also have implications for the wider context of this interview about how we provide guidance and support.

The other issue is who, then, is responsible for providing that guidance and support? Because some of those topics around data quality blur the lines between research data management and training in research skills and practice. It's not the job of the Library to tell people how to do data collection, processing and analysis, but data cleaning and data validation blur that boundary.

Those aspects of how to go around collecting [and] processing analysed data [are] not something that research data management covers [or] the Library teaches. Are there other ways in which that training is delivered? For the Graduate School, we deliver some workshops under the Research Integrity strand. But there's another strand about computational data research, which includes training in Python and R, the data science side of things. Is data quality one of things that could fall between the cracks?

Colling, David J 15:05

Isn't part of the issue here that data quality is very subject/domain-specific?

Peters, Wayne 15:15

Yes. When we touch upon it in our training, I tend to speak at a very high level of things like calibration of instruments or following standard operating procedures where they're in place. And, again, that's why we tend to focus on the spreadsheet, because that allows us to be a little bit more detailed, but it's generally things like peer review of data, double input of data, those kinds of things. But if you want to talk about it specifically then you really need someone who's doing the research. That's the challenge.

ter Wal, Anne 15:57

In the social sciences, there are two main [objectives] that are pushing towards open data.

There have been some high-profile cases of intellectual or academic fraud. The lowest hanging fruit is in the sense that if data are available or subsets of data are shared, it allows for better editorial oversight and peer review. Luckily, [that's] still on a case-by-case basis. These are slowly but surely changing the landscape.

The bigger picture, though, is what is called the replication crisis. In the social sciences, much more so than in the natural sciences, it's difficult sometimes to replicate research, so it's not very often done. There's little value in [it], unfortunately, given the emphasis placed on novelty when it comes to publishing. Replication is a forgotten part of the game to begin with. But when it is being done, things often don't turn out to be very replicable at all, so making data available to enable replication to become [a] more integral part of the repertoire of activities that we undertake in research is a second objective.

These two approaches have different repercussions for the policies we're trying to shape. Open data to ensure the quality of what is being published versus enabling future replication are two very different objectives that might call for quite different responses, for example, from the perspective of a journal like AMJ [Academy of Management Journal].

Colling, David J 17:57

You're talking about publication policies in social sciences. Talking to my bioinformatics friends and colleagues, they point out, one of the big changes to their subject area, more than a decade ago, maybe 15 years ago, was that journals refused to accept any papers if they didn't put the sequence into one of the well-known databases for everybody to use. That apparently was a real game-changer.

Khan, Hamid 18:39

And was there pushback in terms of commercial sensitivity or the sorts of concerns that we still hear in many fields?

Colling, David J 18:48

There was initially, but the journal [pressed ahead], and so eventually they fell into line. More than a year ago, I presented our FAIR data plans to the College Research Committee, and the only negative thing that came back was some people on the committee were concerned about commercial opportunities being lost.

The other thing is reproducibility is not just a problem for social sciences. I can see it being a specific problem, but if you've got a scientific instrument in the physical sciences where there's only one of them – the Cassini probe or some other Space mission – those datasets are not going to be reproduced anytime soon. Similarly, where I work at the LHC, there are two general-purpose experiments, [of] which I work on one. There is a cross-check there, but the designs of the experiments are deliberately sufficiently different that we can't take ATLAS [a piece of equipment at the LHC] data and our data and interchange them. So, there can be other ways of being unique.

Khan, Hamid 20:20

We've talked a little bit about commercial sensitivities. What do you think are some of the other challenges to implementing a system where the default is for data to be open?

McArdle, Ian J 20:42

I still think a big part of it is awareness of what's required and what's already in place, even support-wise. Even if you just look at the feedback from the workshops [the four scoping and co-creation workshops held with Imperial researchers, professional staff and members of the public from April to July 2024], people were suggesting things as good ideas that are already in place, but there's just not that awareness, which is very hard to do across Imperial, let alone the entire sector.

We've got [few] departments compared to UCL [University College London], Oxford, Cambridge, but even then, we've got 30-odd very distinct entities. It's hard to get [a] message down to individuals. However we do that, I think a key bit is trying to translate funder requirements and College policy, which generally go hand in hand, to individuals, but to let them know there is support in place, [that] there are these requirements there, we are trying to implement these systems and “here's what you can do in the meantime”.

It's not really second nature for a lot of academics to go on a webpage and search for guidance for what the College is already doing. I think we need to find more effective ways of getting the message across. Hopefully things like the FAIR data repository will do that. For those that don't have their own domain-specific [repositories], or it's not the norm in their domain to be publishing in this way, having that in place could be crucial. Trying to really embed that into the processes will be the important thing.

ter Wal, Anne 23:12

I'm fully in favour of making open data the default. In the social sciences, there are two types of research that would typically not lend themselves so well to that or at least I would expect a lot of resistance, the first one being qualitative research – so interview research or research based on archival sources of information that are often quite confidential. Very few interview participants would very easily give their consent if they [knew] that information [would] be publicly available.

A lot of research in the Business School, for example, is about highly sensitive topics, gender discrimination, those kinds of topics, data within organisations. You would understand that organisations would not typically be very comfortable having that data out in public databases, even if it's being anonymised. That will be the first strand of research where anonymisation is difficult because there's a lot of information. Even if names and organisations are being masked, it often doesn't take a genius to figure out who might be talking and the organisations that are involved.

The second is, in response to David's comment, in the social sciences, a much smaller portion of research is publicly funded or at least funded by research councils, [so] not as directly affected by the mandate of research councils and other funders to make research data public.

Those two forces are at play. That would make the Business School probably less advanced in terms of making data open by default. One of the six top journals in our field is mandating this and making it the default. It is slowly but surely changing. But there are [the] two bits of background that probably explain why this is, at least as it stands, not the default in the field that I'm playing in.

Peters, Wayne 25:40

The biggest challenge in my role, which is to provide support and guidance, especially when it comes to data sharing, has been the gap between the funder and publisher requirements [on one side] and the infrastructure that's available to support researchers to enable them to meet those requirements [on the other side], especially around sensitive or confidential data. Where data can be made openly available without risk, it's reasonably straightforward. That's assuming the documentation and the metadata [are] in place.

In terms of confidentiality issues, often when we talk to researchers, a lot of the dialogue isn't really about sharing data openly. It's about sharing data in ways that can satisfy ethical and legal requirements. We talk about controlled access to data, and one of the challenges is that there aren't that many repositories which provide that kind of restricted access. The social sciences [are] better served than most because of the UK Data Service, which does provide tiered access to social science datasets. Hopefully, the things we've been talking about already – the data repository, and there's a TRE [Trusted Research Environment] that's going live at some point – will provide that technical infrastructure.

One of the frustrations that we often have, or researchers have, is: "My funder says share the data in a way that's controlled and can meet the funder requirements, but where can I put it to do that?" And what we've been asked is that the data repository be able to provide mediated access to sensitive data, and that can range from data which is low-risk under the GDPR [UK General Data Protection Regulation] but still shouldn't be made publicly available to more sensitive data.

The message we always put across is that no one's going to tell researchers to openly share data that they can't make publicly available. I do understand you get this pushback, especially around commercial data. All the funder policies say share data openly as long as it does not infringe upon ethical [or] legal constraints. I think that's been the gap so far.

So, we're in a 'fingers-crossed' threshold here in terms of the support we can provide, particularly around sensitive [or] confidential data. If the infrastructure gets put in place, then we're going to be in a much better position to be able to alleviate

some of those difficulties that researchers face when they have data that can't be made openly available.

The other point about [researchers] being less likely to receive public funding in the Business School is an interesting one. That's come up before as one of the reasons why we rarely get researchers from the Business School come to us to, say, review data management plans, because they're just not being asked to do them. The other pressure, then, would be through the publishers and the journals, as David mentioned: if you've got a journal, especially if it's a "prestige" journal, and it says it won't publish unless you make the data available, or at least explain how someone can access the data or what the reasons are why it can't be made available.

McArdle, Ian J 29:44

On the data management plan points specifically, even though it's not required by all funders, it is required by the College for all externally funded research. It's highlighting that perhaps we haven't embedded that policy as well as we could have done, that there isn't that awareness. Just because the funder doesn't say it's needed, doesn't mean it's not needed.

Colling, David J 31:45

We ran a survey 18 months ago, where we surveyed every grant PI in College and we got about a 10-12% response rate, which was pretty low, but it's still 200 replies, 207 or 208, something like that. The only thing that [hasn't come up in this conversation is] it takes time and effort to make your data publicly available, and people were asking for help and more guidance on doing this.

One of the objectives of the third data exercise we're doing is [that], as well as being able to cope with sensitive data or different categories, we need to make it really easy for [researchers] to publish data.

Large data is the other thing. If you're publishing datasets above a certain size, you can't get them into a place like Zenodo [a general open data repository], but we will have it in the College repository.

On the sociological side of things, we should emphasise the benefits of publishing data. Common benefits [cited] were: your data is reused by other people, your work

is cited more often. In my field, it means that the people who are trying to interpret results from different experiments will take your data rather than rival data.

One of my colleagues in physics, a climate change person, says that often ESA [European Space Agency] data is better than NASA data. But NASA data is much easier to get hold of and to understand, because the metadata is better and it's a nicer interface. So, when he's comparing his simulation to the available measurements, his first call is to go to NASA data rather than ESA data.

So, I think, if we tell people, "Make it available so that people can use it," they will use it and they will cite your papers, and in doing so you may form collaborations. Your work is more important when people use it.

Khan, Hamid 34:40

Having read [the FAIR data survey], I saw that there was a focus on the benefits of data transparency. What are some of the tangible benefits of data transparency that we need to be talking about?

Peters, Wayne 35:16

What's interesting is the barriers and benefits live in mirror, in inverse relation to each other. [A] barrier might be that researchers are worried about being scooped [where another author publishes your idea before you]. But, contrary to that, researchers who did express benefits said that they were given additional credit, they got additional citations for their research by publishing the data, or they were added as additional authors to papers. There are worries about being scooped. [Balanced against that] is the opportunity to get credit for your data.

People were worried about having their data being misunderstood or wilfully misrepresented. But again, if your data is being cited and it's got a DOI [digital object identifier] that's out there, then it's much easier to challenge if someone is misusing your data. It's less likely to be misunderstood.

There is also an incentive to making sure that the data you put out and the code you put out is good quality because people are going to be looking at it. Again, it means that you're more likely to get credit for it.

Another one that people say, understandably, is that preparing data to be shared takes up a lot of time and resources, which it does, but then others did say [that] if you share the data right in a repository, [you] don't have to keep responding to requests to share it. And a few people said: "I know where my own data is. If I put it in a repository, a few years later I know where it is. If I can't find it amongst my own files, I know it's in Zenodo or whatever."

Collaboration was another one that came up, which I thought was [a] really positive sign. When we do the theory, we say the benefit is there are more collaborations, so it's actually really good to hear researchers at Imperial say it did actually lead to more collaborations.

ter Wal, Anne 38:39

I agree with all the benefits that have been discussed so far. One I would add is the opportunity for training doctoral students and junior researchers. Playing around with data is an important element, and what I see, for example, with my own doctoral students, is that they often rush to analysing data before knowing your data, being able to just see what a dataset behind the published paper actually looks like. What kind of patterns do you see, just descriptively, if you probe the data with much more advanced methods? There are major training opportunities around availability of data that underpins published research. That is possibly one of the bigger advantages that might just help convince people.

I do think that the advantages of open data helping to prevent academic fraud are overstated. At Harvard Business School, there's a professor, Francesca Gino. Her work is actually part of the paradigm where there is a high standard of open data, where experimental research data are in full provided in online repositories such as the OSF [Open Science Framework], and it took a team of committed people to split hairs on those Excel sheets that she uploaded. [They discovered] that, if you try to replicate the original versions that were first downloaded, she added rows of data that she manipulated, likely. Very atypical responses occurred multiple times in a data set which raised a few flags.

But that really requires a level of engagement with the data that, for example, a peer reviewer would not be willing to commit to. That means even in a part of the social sciences where there is a mandate to make your research data available in open

repositories, we still do see fraud. I think [openness and transparency are] not necessarily going to stop people. If we emphasise this as the biggest advantage, first of all, it's a very negative message. [The idea of] policing [the] research field, I don't think that is necessarily going to take away the nervousness that people have in making data openly available.

The benefits, some of which you've talked about in terms of citations, but also training opportunities, those are ultimately much more persuasive, at least to convince academic stakeholders in putting in the time and effort to prepare data for openly sharing and so forth.

McArdle, Ian J 41:35

There are funder-specific [benefits]. We want to keep our funders happy, otherwise they don't fund our research. You're not going to do a great deal if you if you wind them up.

There are certain funders who, if you don't necessarily comply with various terms and conditions, you don't come eligible for future funding either. That's quite a key one to keep them on-side.

Khan, Hamid 42:06

The conversation so far has focussed on data related to publications, positive data. What about negative data? What can we do to encourage people to share data from experiments that haven't worked?

ter Wal, Anne 42:36

Yes. That's a huge issue in social sciences. The only research that we see is the research that has been successful [or] found something. Anything that has unsupported results, unsupported hypotheses, is just having great difficulty to get published, so we don't see that. I don't see this changing very soon.

One thing that would be quite interesting, with the increasing amount of research that is being pre-registered, where researchers are publicly claiming they're going to perform a particular study, it would be possible for somebody with reasonable data skills to see what percentage of that research actually does get published. Can we find traces of that research four, five [or] six years down the line?

Research timelines can be quite long, and I wouldn't be surprised if a lot of research that is being done is not anywhere being published. Sometimes, [the] first two or three studies are not part of the published work, and studies four, five and six are, so we don't see the full picture in one particular publication. And sometimes we don't see research being published at all.

I think it does two things. One is it does provide a perverse incentive for people to manipulate their data in ways that they're going to find support for their hypothesis. It is an incredibly important challenge to address. I don't think we have found a suitable way to change the incentives, in this respect.

Khan, Hamid 44:22

Is pre-registration the main way that we can encourage sharing of negative data? Are there other ideas [to] think about?

Colling, David J 44:45

For social sciences and medical sciences, pre-registration makes a lot of sense. For things in the physical sciences, generally it doesn't.

Thinking about my own field, if you look for a new particle and you don't find it, you publish the paper saying [you] haven't found it, because this is information that other people can use: they know you've searched that part of the parameter space and not found anything there. That's different from trying to build [a] detector and it [doesn't] work because there's too much internal reflection or something like that. Unless some principle hasn't worked, making it worth publishing, if it hasn't worked for technical reason, no one is really interested. If there's a detection principle that's not worked, then yes.

But I can't think of any physical sciences area where pre-registration would be a useful idea. I think, again, the solution is domain-specific.

McArdle, Ian J 46:22

One of the reasons the funders cited for publishing your data in the first place [is that] they were saying you should make all your findings available, because if it's cost £5 million to find out it doesn't work, we don't want someone three years later

asking for another £5 million to prove the same things. That was one of the principles we didn't quite mirror in our policy. We've said, "Underpin your published findings."

Of course, that goes down to what people [and] publishers are willing to publish, as well as what we want to tell the world, which is a slightly harder thing. But ideally if we do have our own repository internally, there are free options for doing it – free from a certain perspective. Obviously, if it takes a researcher quite a while to put it together, that's not free in terms of their salary, et cetera and resource. But, yes, it is one of the original principles from the funders' perspectives.

I'm not entirely sure what we mean by pre-registration. Is it that what you're trying to do effectively?

Khan, Hamid 47:48

Yes, it would be pre-registration of your protocol, your methods, your expected data analysis as a way of creating a record of the research before it has been done and therefore creating an expectation that it would be reported back on, even if it hasn't worked.

McArdle, Ian J 48:04

Most public funders will publish that they have funded a grant. That does exist to some degree for, I'd say, quite a chunk of our funding. You can find a public record from a lot of our funders.

Khan, Hamid 48:17

Yes, to some degree on the funder side, you can find a public record, through Dimensions, for example. [Preregistration] is being engaged with in different ways. Increasingly, publishers and journals are starting to engage with pre-registration to a greater degree than funders have done, e.g., peer reviewing those pre-registered reports. It's a question of degrees.

ter Wal, Anne 49:07

Although pre-registration is quite common in some of the social sciences, including business research, a lot of social sciences research is not very suitable to fit the pre-registration requirement, and that has to do with a lot of academic research in

general, but certainly in the social sciences. It's iterative in nature. Pre-registration presupposes that you have a plan, you conduct it and that's it. You report, you find. Research is a lot more iterative than that in a lot of cases. This is true even in experimental research, but much more so in research based on other types of methods.

There is a danger that we're trying to impose a template of increasing transparency that works for a part of the social sciences and other forms of science. So, "iterative" in the natural sciences might be just about the technical hurdles to overcome you didn't foresee, and that requires you to take a different approach [than you] originally had in mind. There's nothing fundamentally wrong with that. Particularly if research is highly iterative, you can't just comment on or update all of the single things that you're doing all the time. It just becomes too laborious. So, to some extent, maybe it's naïve, but there must be some trust in academic integrity that iteration and adaptation is part of what we do.

The conversation is probably not finished about how to do this in ways that help us to be more ethical and transparent, but [that] doesn't become a one-size-fits-all' template. It doesn't work for many of us.

Khan, Hamid 51:15

I want to turn back to some of the topics mentioned both in this call and during the workshops, around the idea of peer review, not just of manuscripts and publications, but of data, as well.

This was an idea that workshop participants latched on to as a possible solution to the challenge of quality. What do you think about that concept of peer review of data? Is it feasible, and if so, what would we need to consider in order to develop it?

Peters, Wayne 52:03

I think it comes back to the point that Anne made earlier [that it] could be negative just focussing on fighting fraud. One of the reservations that researchers have about sharing data and code is that they're worried about the quality of the data and code they've used. People might find errors in it, and one way of dealing that would be to have some kind of peer review process in place so that code – [CodeCheck](#) is one thing for code – and data could be checked before it gets published. That may be a

way of both allaying researchers' fears, but [also] helping to improve the quality of the code if it's needed.

Now, who's going to do that and how that's going [to be done], I don't know. For the repository, for example, we will carry [out] a review of the datasets that are deposited, but we will review the metadata and a very light touch with the data. Does the file open? Is the file what it's supposed to be? But we're not going to look at the broader question of errors in the data. We're not going to look at the scientific quality of the data. Who's going to do it? Some journals have made it part of their policies, some publishers have included peer review of data as one of the policy levers that they have, but I don't know how many journals actually do it or have the resources to do that.

The other [challenge is] this idea of not imposing a 'one-size-fits-all'. I can see how that in principle can be done with quantitative data, but is that necessarily relevant for qualitative data? If you've got interviews, I can't really tell you whether the data is correct or not. It comes back to [whether] the conclusions are plausible based on the [data]. That might be the other issue to consider, as well.

So, who's going to do it? And what's appropriate for different kinds of data in different domains?

Colling, David J 54:09

It's a really difficult area. I'm trying to think about my own [field]. Where I work, there are so many cross-checks being done all the time by different groups of people and such large experiments, and there's the internal peer reviewing process of any publication. But that inherently asks the authors of each individual paper to try different data selections to start with and looks for any abnormalities there. To some extent, it's happening, but not in any uniform or rigorous way, and I think having somebody review LHC data for a journal, for example, would just not be feasible. I can see in some situations [it] might be possible, but then again, what are you trying to check?

I'm making this example up, so it may well be flawed in many ways. If you're working at Diamond [Diamond Light Source, a research facility based in Oxfordshire] and you're trying a variety of detectors to make your measurement, if one of those

detectors isn't working for some reason – the voltage isn't high enough or whatever – how would somebody else reviewing your data spot that? [Note: Ian McArdle left the call at this point.] If you're doing the job well, you'll see that maybe it's less efficient, so you get less signal at that detector and that will flag up to you as something wrong. But if you don't see anything, or you see less than you expected and you assume it's working, and if that's a scientifically interesting result, then you can publish something that's completely wrong, but no amount of checking by a third party would ever pick that up. It would be extraordinarily difficult to do.

Space missions are somewhat similar to the environment where I work, where there's so many people working on them, and each one is trying to understand the data as well as they can. There's lots of internal cross-checking going on already, and it's hard to see how any external body could ever come close to doing a better job than what's already being done by the people looking at the data.

In large science, there's almost no capacity for intellectual fraud. It's much more likely to happen in experiments with one or two people working on them or areas like some social sciences where it might be easy to create false data if you've done a survey, say. But in large science, there's so many people cross-checking everything, and quite rightly, too, because these experiments cost hundreds of millions or billions of pounds – the LHC doesn't come cheap, so it's right that people are cross-checking everything.

Certainly in physical sciences, I don't see how it's realistically possible, and even [in] the social sciences, it would require people doing scrutiny on spreadsheets, finding anomalous things there. That's going to be a large piece of work, and you can't expect that to be done for every paper published. Somebody [needs to] have said [they] think there's something odd about these results and therefore somebody put the time and effort to do the analysis. That's a very simple case, as simple a case as it gets. So, yes, it's very difficult.

Peters, Wayne 58:32

But what you're saying, David, brings us back to transparency again. The key thing is to make sure that all those quality checks are documented, so that even if someone can, if feasible, asked peer review the data, at least you can see that there have been

quality checks in place. That doesn't mean, of course, there won't be errors, and I think that's important to get the distinction between errors and fraud.

There are sincere errors, which are part of science and people shouldn't be punished for, but if you can see that it's gone through procedures, then that tells you something about the quality and the integrity of the data, even if you can't actually [do] peer review.

Colling, David J 59:22

You make two really good points there. My supervisor, all his PhD students – of which I was his last and Professor Sir Tejinder Virdee FRS [Fellow of the Royal Society] was his first – the only thing we all agree on, that he taught us, was: “The only people who don't make mistakes are the people who don't do anything.” And that's a really important thing. You will make mistakes. Don't make too many, but when you make them, stick your hands up and say: “Look, I made this mistake, or I made this assumption [and] it was wrong.”

On the experiments on CMS [the Compact Muon Solenoid, one of the pieces of equipment on the Large Hadron Collider], we have we have three types of publications. We have the regular journal papers, which is where most things go. We have what we call PAS's, which stands for Physics Analysis Summaries, which are interim results that we make available for conferences before the main paper comes out. But the third one is technical papers, which aren't published anywhere other than our websites, and these will often be the cross-checks and the measurements of the efficiencies, of all the things that we're talking about. Sometimes, those go into the main publication or as backup materials. We do publish a lot of backup material on a subject-specific website, but if they don't [go there], we make them available as these public technical notes. These are really important.

ter Wal, Anne 1:01:19

First, I wanted to echo David's point. Maybe I'm on the reservation side of things. I think data peer review [sits] a little bit uncomfortably with the idea that raw data are perfect. We spend a lot of time ironing out inconsistencies, cleaning up data in some ways, and these are human judgments that are very difficult to document because it will almost near endless. But also it's a matter of judgment. Where does fraud start and where does data cleaning end? I think it's not very obvious.

I told my doctoral student the other day: "If you see an entrepreneur in your dataset that has a reported age [of] 108, there's something wrong, right?" Possibly they're taking the year 1900 as opposed to the year 2000 as a starting point or something like that. If you engage with the data in depth, you'll actually observe those things. If you find unjustified patterns in the data, then you can justify correcting those mistakes.

However, thinking more of possibilities as opposed to reservations, one thing I would envision is more of a two-stage peer review process. In cases where research is perhaps a little less iterative, you can submit a research proposal in terms of what [you're] going to do, what's [your] experimental design, what is [your] survey design or what is [your] research question, and that is being peer-reviewed based on the academic merit. Then, in a second stage, it is not totally inconceivable to say we're going to scrutinise the data as well as the interpretations and conclusions derived from them. A two-stage process of peer review, of the design of the study, by and large, and the analysis and interpretation as a second step, for the social sciences a model like that is something that we should try.

It might not work for everything, but I think there is at least a chunk of social science research that would quite possibly fit in that paradigm. And I think it would resolve potentially the negative research findings issue that talked about. It would resolve the fraud side of things potentially, too. I think it is an important thing that we should try as a field, but I'm personally not aware of this being tried out yet, at least in [the field of] management.

Khan, Hamid 1:03:40

It sounds like it's a case of, not so much peer reviewing the data itself, but peer reviewing the processes around the data to ensure that they have been followed. When we talk about peer review of data, perhaps that's the balance that we need to strike.

Now, I don't want to take up anymore of your time. There are a few more questions to ask, but I'll follow up by email, and you're very welcome to respond to those in your own time if that's okay.

I'll also follow up just to explain what's going to happen next and how this data that we've generated as part of this interview will be treated, as well.

Lastly, I just want to thank you for your time. I really appreciate that everyone is taking the time to do this. I feel like we're making progress, and I think we will get some practical ideas out of this project that I'm looking forward to sharing with you. Thank you very much.